

Integration of Lean and Six Sigma Methodologies In organization

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ABSTRACT : Goals for industries. This thesis explores the integration of Value Stream Analysis (VSA) and Value Stream Mapping (VSM) within the DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, Control) framework of Lean Six Sigma to enhance project success. The research highlights how these methodologies complement each other and contribute to process improvements. A key focus of this study is to develop a structured approach for conducting a comprehensive VSA, enabling industries to identify inefficiencies and drive continuous improvement. Additionally, the research investigates which Lean tools, such as Gemba, 5S, Pareto analysis, Poka-yoke, FIFO rails, root cause analysis, and visual management, are applied in each phase of DMAIC. The study also presents a practical methodology for optimizing picking workstations, commonly found in manufacturing plants, aiming to create an environment with minimal process variability, enhanced error visibility, and ergonomic workflow design.

Keywords- Lean, Six Sigma, Lean Six Sigma, Process Improvement, Continuous Improvement etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a fast-changing market, it is crucial for industries to be able to adapt to different levels of production. Some industries are using statistical methodologies and Lean practices in their daily life. There are two complementary methodologies, widely adopted across industries: Lean and Six Sigma. While Lean has a strong focus on value and eliminating waste from the production process, Six Sigma focuses on reducing defects and sources of variability. The unification of both philosophies is Lean Six Sigma (LSS), and it is characterized by finding the roots of the problems from a quantitative approach and implementing well-thought and tested improvements. Many industries have adopted LSS tools, and its implementation has been proved successful.

LSS framework and tools provide a deep understanding of value and help companies have a balanced production mix, low costs and low variability. Although these LSS tools are useful to improve many areas of the production, they often do not provide a systematic process that helps the production to improve coherently and continuously in time [1].

The value and originality of this thesis is to show how VSA and VSM are used with DMAIC to carry out successful projects, and to identify how those practices can benefit each other in a project. Secondly, another objective is to develop a detailed description on how to carry out a full VSA, which will enable industries to evolve in the good direction and to identify key improvements. The third objective of this research is to understand which Lean tools are integrated in each phase of the DMAIC process. The tools used on this project will be the following: Value-Stream mapping, Gemba, 5S, Pareto diagrams, Poka-yoke, First-In-First-Out (FIFO) rails, Root cause analysis and Visual management. Finally, the most practical objective of this thesis is to provide a methodology and an example on how to improve picking workstations. Similar

workstations are often found in manufacturing plants. This thesis tries to describe and assess improvements that will create a process with almost no variability, in which the errors are spotted at simple sight and the movements are all comfortable, quick and predictable [2].

II.LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, there will be a review of the literature around Six Sigma, Lean principles and understanding of value, and the use around the industries of Lean Six Sigma and DMAIC methodology. At the end, there will be a focus on the integration of Value-Stream mapping in Lean Six Sigma. The origins of this methodology can be traced at 1986 with Six Sigma in Motorola (United States) and the already existing Lean Manufacturing in Toyota (Japan). It combines identifying and removing the causes of defects, minimizing variability and eliminating non-value adding activities [3].

2.1 Six Sigma

Six Sigma is a doctrine, which asserts the continuous improvement to achieve stable and predictable results, by stating that the characteristics in business processes are quantitative. In addition, it encourages a supportive management style that is driven by data, statistics and returns, not on assumptions and guesswork. In fact, the term Six Sigma refers to the Standard deviation (σ) symbol in a Gauss distribution. In a bell-shaped curve, the distance of 6 standard deviation correspond to 99,7% of the data. The purpose of Six Sigma is defined by the aim of having a small variability, without outliers in a process. Six Sigma has two different models: DMAIC is suitable for process optimization, and Design for Six Sigma (DFSS) is useful in product design. The DMAIC methodology has been used widely in many industrial fields, as well as services, healthcare and logistics. On the other hand, Six Sigma is frequently combined with Lean management, which is a similar methodology because it is also based on data and continuous improvement. However, Six Sigma is more of a methodology, while Lean management is a more generic philosophy. The combination of the two practices, which appears in the beginning of the 2000s decade, is called Lean Six Sigma [4].

2.2. Lean

Lean is a broad term that applies to almost all aspects across industries. Although there are many ways to define Lean, all the definitions can be simplified by providing customer satisfaction and therefore, being profitable. Lean is often called Agile, or stock-free manufacturing, which tries to avoid baGalaxy Industryhes and stock, and therefore being able to quickly adapt to any change and correct any misdirection [5]. One of the focus of Lean is the understanding of value, as it is defined as something that the customer is willing to pay for, and of the waste, which is the absence of value in an activity. In fact, many scholars divide the activities in three types: Value Adding (VA), Non-Value Adding (NVA), and Necessary Non-Value Adding (NNVA). NNVA, are also called Value Enabling, as they do not add value by themselves but are necessary for adding value in other activities. Lean has a framework for carrying out projects called Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA). Just like DMAIC, PDCA is a quantitative, iterative approach that looks for root causes. This two approaches are very similar and many companies opt for any of them with very similar results [6].

2.3. Lean Manufacturing and Six Sigma equivalence

The claim that Lean and Six Sigma have a complementary relationship is widely accepted, and there are many experiences where companies coach each other in their respective methodologies. As an example, Boeing is a leader in Lean and General Electric is a leader in Six Sigma. There is an agreement that DMAIC is more adequate for carrying out projects, and the Lean contribution to DMAIC is more related to Lean principles [7]. Both methodologies are similar and can be complementary. In general, PDCA puts more emphasis in the execution and in the cyclic nature of improvement, while DMAIC emphasizes the identification of the root causes of the problems and the planning phase. Their equivalence is widely accepted as being as shown in [8].

Figure 1. PDCA and DMAIC equivalence

Salah et al. (2019) mention that DMAIC is better than PDCA because it is a more comprehensive and robust structure, and it can still include the Lean tools in a way. In fact, they say one of the challenges of LSS is choose the adequate tools for each DMAIC phase. Therefore, even though both methodologies are similar, there should be a better way for Lean to complement Six Sigma. The goal of Lean Six Sigma is to use a common vision and a language that integrates both Lean and Six Sigma. LSS initiatives will transform organizations into cross-functional process as long as there is a good understanding of its practices, principles and tools. The best summary of the Lean principles can be found in the book '*Lean solutions*' by Womack and Jones (2015) [10].

2.2. Value in Lean Six Sigma: customer satisfaction and absence of waste

Value is commonly defined by: everything the customer is willing to pay for. Alternatively, Lean Six Sigma can also have a different approach, by identifying Waste, which is absence of Value.

2.2.1. Value as customer satisfaction

Figure 2- 3-dimensional approach to a commodity

In order to understand what Value is, first there is a customer to be identified, whose priorities must be understood. Identifying a customer is not trivial, because there can be external and internal customers, with very different interests. Customer satisfaction has a triple approach, which is commonly defined as QCD (Quality, Cost and Delivery) that are the three ways customers mainly appreciate value. The three dimensional approach of a commodity was defined in the 70s by the British automobile sector and summarized by Imai in the book '*Gemba Kaizen: a Commonsense, Low-cost approach to Management*' (2017) [11].

Quality is the attribute desired by the user or buyer that renders the product its primary value and usefulness to him. Proper tolerances, specifications, features, and varieties are examples of quality indicators. Many Lean practices are focused in providing reliable and robust products. Even though providing the best quality can be difficult in the short-term, developing suppliers and embracing a culture that exposes mistakes and bad practices will lead to top-quality in the long-term [12].

Cost, the second dimension, refers to the cost of producing and delivering the product to the customer; it has an impact on another cost: the cost to the buyer or the "price" he pays for the good. Cost affects the marketability of the product and the profitability of the producer. The Lean approach to cost is mainly about using resources in the most efficient way, which is the same to say 'avoiding waste'. There are generally 8 types of waste, also called *muda*, as summarized by the acronym TIMWOODS. Transport, Inventory, Motion, Waiting, Overproduction, Over-processing, Defects and the newly added, Skill. The third way to provide customer satisfaction by Lean is Delivery, which has to do with time. Delivery involves bringing the finished goods or services to the customer at the right time, at the right quantity or amount, at the right place. Lean is a timely system that ensures customers the products when they want them. Thanks to avoiding variability in processes, the delivery time can be predicted. there are many Lean tools related to standardizing and having little unforeseen results [12].

2.3. Lean Six Sigma

2.3.1. Lean Six Sigma practices in the industry

There are many examples of implementing the LSS approach in a manufacturing industry. More concretely, Small and Medium enterprises constitute the bulk of the major contribution to all the economies of the India, and especially in India. (Antony, Kumar, & Madu, Six Sigma in small and medium sized UK manufacturing enterprises, 2025). They are key for the jobs in all areas of business: production, finance, marketing and even personal management [13].

Zhou (2016) studied more than 200 medium and small enterprises in the United States, and stated that most of enterprises have an accurate understanding of Lean principles and that they have a positive impact on their performance [14].

Chiarini (2014) studied five Indian motorcycle components manufacturing enterprises that implemented different Lean tools and he discovered that Lean practices not only had an impact on waste inside the production, but also had a positive impact environmentally [15].

In India, Panwar et al. (2015) declared that Lean practices are still not applied across industries, although it has been implemented in some enterprises and have had good results, primarily reducing waste and increasing quality [16].

Also China has been focus of some research, Taj (2018) studied 65 manufacturing plants in China, and found that the implementation of Lean was led by oil industries, but also in computer, telecommunications and electronics industries [17].

Jasti and Kodali (2024) studied the academic output of Lean practices research, and they proposed that the focus of researches should be on creating and testing new hypothesis, mainly thanks to techniques like case studies and surveys. Nowadays, 63.82% of the empirical research in the Lean Six Sigma literature uses actual data for research and can control and validate the process (Thomas, Ringwald, Parfitt, Davies, & John, 2024) [18-19].

During the last two decades, the majority of the journal articles have been limited to very few sectors, mainly manufacturing, healthcare, automotive and electronic industries. In addition, the focus of these articles has been to test tools, obtain benefits and understand the success factors (Shokri, 2017) [20].

III. VALUE STREAM ANALYSIS

3.1 Value Stream Analysis

Every year, the managers of the company hold an annual Value-Stream analysis, which consists in a 5 days (40 hours) meeting that involves all the managers of the company. Value Stream Analysis is a standard process for measuring, understanding, and improving the flow and interactions of all the associated tasks across the enterprise to keep the cost, service and quality of a company's products and services as competitive as possible [21].

The objective is to improve cycle time in existing process, even if Lean tools have already been applied. Also, continue to mature knowledge and skills of new and existing employees using Lean concepts. The Operational Excellence team facilitates the VSA, and all the managers and relevant people in the organization appear and discuss some topics in order to improve the manufacturing process. A value stream perspective means working on the big picture, not just optimizing the parts. The outputs of the value-stream analysis is the following:

1. A Cross-functional team will look at every process required to maintain the business and there will be structured and unstructured discussions to identify key areas of improvement.
2. Graphical representation of all the processes, both showing product flow and information flow.
3. One Current Value Stream Map with the current state of the company observed by the team (CVSM).
4. Another Future Value Stream Map with the future state after one year (FVSM)
5. A plan on how to get from the Current VSM to the future VSM, with a transformation schedule to follow during the next 12 months.

If the VSA is successful, it will provide with meaningful opportunities for improvement and will create a common ground for all the managers to resolve proactively the next generation of issues. The principles guiding the facilitation of the VSA are:

- Get everyone involved: hands-on work, look for ideas everywhere
- Identify root causes: it's a problem-solving tool
- Turn ideas into action, target waste and plan
- Develop a plan with a sequence of events

3.1.1 Execution of VSA

There are 4 basic steps in a VSA, as appear in Figure 3.

Figure 3-Basic steps of a VSA.

Defining customer expectations: helps determine appropriate scope and start with the appropriate mindset. It's useful to understand the competition and our value proposition, and focuses on service and delivery.

Value stream mapping: creates product families, documents the current state, visions the future state and puts together a project pipeline to transform the industrial activity. Pays attention to material and information flow. In a lower level of detail there will be also an analysis of people's flow. The level of detail is door to door, which means that start when the raw materials enter the company and ends when finished products leave. It considers each workstation as a black box, with inputs and outputs.

Value analysis: walk the whole value adding process and visually look for the 8 wastes exist. Differentiating between VA, NVA, and NNVA. The later will be where most opportunities will appear.

VS plan & Review Process: After identifying opportunities, there will be high-level discussions on possible measures and projects to carry out during the next 12 months. After identifying these projects and a rough estimate on the resources involved, the managers will schedule and plan the time and resources given to each project.

In the Value Stream analysis, the company will map the plant, with all the processes that add value to the products, establishing pull and measuring all the inventories. This part is crucial because it will provide ideas for many improvements or projects to execute during the following year in the company. The advantages of starting with this analysis, to name some, are the following:

- It makes the managers share their problems
- Understand the production as a whole
- Decides the priorities for the next year
- Facilitates cultural change and a Lean framework

Out of all the ideas that come out of the VSM, a project will be selected, and the DMAIC methodology will start [22].

3.2 DMAIC: carrying out the project

Define: in this part, the problem will be defined, explaining the scope, team, timeline and goals of the project. Some typical parts of the define phase overlap with the VSM, however, most of the material related to project management will be produced in this phase.

Measure: it consists in the data collection of the process, to understand what improvements to expect, with concrete measurements to seize the waste. There will be some KPI selected and observed. Thanks to this phase, we can start having an idea of the problems in the current state. In this phase there will be very detailed descriptions of the current process and some Kaizen events.

Analyze: after having identified the waste, in the analyze part there will be hypothesis to find the sources of the errors and waste, and some ideas will be drafted to be tested afterwards. There will be attention to different types of errors, bottlenecks and sources of variation. Thanks to the ideas

gathered in this part, new improvements will start to emerge.

Improve: in this phase is when the ideas for the testing will be carried out and the project will be materialized. This phase involves most of the work, as requires putting into practice the different solutions and coordinating a large team.

Control: a plan for obtaining data of the new performance will be made and try to prepare contingency plans to avoid bad consequences and ensure the solutions are working [23].

IV.ANALYSIS

The plant is part of the India leader of cooling units, and their customers value specially the delivery and the customization of the product. The company has very large margins compared to the competition, and has higher prices. However, customers are happy with higher prices because of the fast delivery that Galaxy Industry provides. The fast delivery is achieved by a very smooth pull process, many different production levels and a flexible workforce. Galaxy Industry can produce a lot of units without much planning beforehand, and customers know they can rely on them to get cooling units when there are emergencies. Also, they provide service assistance in many different countries of the India, where other manufacturers can't serve quickly. From a financial point of view, the company has a very quick Cash Conversion Cycle, because they can cash in very quickly the customer's orders, while their inventories are always low [24].

4.1 Safety

Current state: There has been 10 years without a single accident in the company, the best efforts have been made on safety, and that's one of the priorities of the plant. The managers agreed that safety is something that should never be compromised, at the expense of any other issue.

KPI: before the company was using the indicator: 'number of consecutive days without any accident in the factory'. However, they decided to change it for a more ambitious one, the KPI they decided to use is: *number of off work days missed by working accident*.

Projects: the company decided to think and develop workstations and activities that require less energy and are very comfortable. Therefore, workers with minor injuries or with special needs can still perform useful work. Managing small inventories of bolts and screws was one idea.

4.2 Delivery

Current state: fast delivery is one of the company's biggest features. GALAXY INDUSTRY promises to deliver units in less than 2-3 days in Southern India, 1 week in Northern India. 3 weeks in Middle East and 4 weeks in America. This is how they have great value added to keep high margins in the selling price.

KPI: the indicator used is '*% of units delivered on time*', as stated in the paragraph above.

Projects: The cases when a unit is not delivered on time is detrimental to a balanced production along the weeks. In fact, any change in the numbers of units assembled/day has an impact on cost and productivity. The team observed that the fails in delivery were mainly during peaks of demand and production. The projects related to this indicator were related to implement rapid changes to production volumes and improving assembly line capability. In order to do that, there needs to be space saved and workstation designed more efficiently, as they are the key aspects that threaten growth.

4.3 Quality

Current state: quality is the aspect where management identifies more room for improvement. The plant is among the worst in requests for repairs and maintenance of units in the company. In fact, they identify that the problem is the rate of problems solved, as they are not classifying the problems in an appropriate way.

KPI: the indicator they will use is '*number of warranty requests earlier less than 6 months after delivery*'. They estimate that most of the losses and customers dissatisfied come quality issues.

Projects: developing a proper diagnosis system and a classifying method for solving quickly quality problems. Once quality problems are properly clustered, it will take less time for quality engineers to work on them.

4.4 Inventories

Current state: the plant has managed to reduce inventories at more than half of their level during the last 5 years. The strategy they followed to achieve that was having less duplicities in the lines. In order to do that, they had to redesign the assembly operations through the line to avoid having the same part in two different workstations. Also, they have less than 3 days delivery for more than 75% of the references. This fact allows the company to have very lean inventories and almost never running out of material.

KPI: the indicator used to measure inventories was '*% of cost of inventories reduced from current level*', and the goal was set at a 10% reduction.

Projects: the strategy will continue by trying to unify workstation and points where the material is kept along the line.

4.5 Employee engagement

Current state: Galaxy Industry has seen a decrease in employee engagement in the last three years. They attribute it mainly to the increasing workload the workers have, and flexibility in their working hours. In fact, many workers complain about having to change very often their workstation, that sometimes they are required to work extra hours with little or no previous information. The managers of the company link the sources of the dissatisfaction to the fact that many workers have to perform some small side jobs when the production is low. When there are not many units assembled, some small jobs that require less time than others require workers moving around the line and adding a lot of waste in unnecessary people movement. Apart from that, Galaxy Industry has a strong commitment with diversity, and believe that improving the rate of people from different origins, as well as different age groups and gender, will improve the current mood in the factory.

KPI: '*the average satisfaction mark that workers give to company during biannual evaluation.*'

Projects: Galaxy Industry needs to find a way to balance the lines better, and be able to adapt and change production levels quickly. Workers will have more stable workstation and there will be less chaos in the lines. The managers see that having more predictable workload will improve the current mood of the factory.

4.6 Growth

Current State: the company has been growing 10% during the last five years. However, it seems that it is not enough, as they are producing more machines every year, and there are around 30% of the weeks at maximum capacity. During the weeks of maximum capacity, any subtle increase of demand will result in units not being delivered on time.

KPI: 'maximum capacity'

Projects: Galaxy Industry needs to find more place for more workers and more workstations in the companies. The managers plan to restructure the lines to have more space for more people, and to unify some workstations that are the same in each line.

V.CONCLUSIONS

For many industries who already apply Lean principles, adopting the complementary Lean and Six Sigma approach enhances their toolbox and possibilities for continuous improvement. However, very often the LSS tools and methods are not useful in deciding which improvement projects should be done. Value Stream Analysis is a very useful technique to engage all the management to focus on value and evolve in the appropriate direction. Thanks to VSA, it will be easy to identify and schedule improvements towards a better manufacturing flow. It is not only useful for the manufacturing flow, but also for employee engagement, relationship with suppliers, reducing costs in all areas and improving communication flow. VSA alone does not provide enough tools or methods to carry out specific project. Furthermore, the lean tools are sometimes very concrete and only useful for short improvements; DMAIC from LSS is a more comprehensive methodology that ensures deep understanding of the root causes and constant improvement. Compared to PDCA from Lean, DMAIC from Six Sigma is more specific in the separation of the different phases, and uses techniques that are more detailed.

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